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Preprint · January 2021

DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.10147.27680/1

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Caffeic Acid and COVID-19

Domina Petric, MD

*I hypothesized in April, 2020 that **caffeic acid**, which is pharmacologically active compound of many medicinal herbs such as *Echinacea purpurea* and *Sambucus Formosana Nakai*, might be a potent molecule for the treatment of COVID-19, especially if pared with Fe^{3+} ions (caffeic acid Fe^{3+} chelate) or other ions (MoO_4^{2-} and PO_4^{3-} chelates), because antiviral activity of caffeic acid increases upwards of 100-fold by the addition of cations (Fe^{3+}) and anionic molecules (molybdate, phosphate). Later on, several researchers confirmed in their reports that caffeic acid and its derivatives may be used against the spread of SARS-CoV-2. Caffeic acid should be tested as prophylaxis and treatment of COVID-19.*

INTRODUCTION

Based on the previous research¹⁻⁴ I hypothesized in April, 2020 that **caffeic acid**, which is pharmacologically active compound of many medicinal herbs such as *Echinacea purpurea* and *Sambucus Formosana Nakai*, might be a potent molecule for the treatment of COVID-19 caused by SARS-CoV-2, especially if pared with Fe^{3+} ions (caffeic acid Fe^{3+} chelate) or other ions (MoO_4^{2-} and PO_4^{3-} chelates), because antiviral activity of caffeic acid increases upwards of 100-fold by the addition of cations (Fe^{3+}) and anionic molecules (molybdate, phosphate).

AN UPDATE

In June, 2020 Kumar and coworkers examined in a study the binding potential of Withaferin-A (Wi-A), Withanone (Wi-N) (active withanolides of Ashwagandha) and **Caffeic Acid Phenethyl Ester** (CAPE, bioactive ingredient of propolis) to a highly conserved protein, M^{PRO} of SARS-CoV-2. Authors found that Wi-N and CAPE, but not Wi-A, bind to the substrate-binding pocket of SARS-CoV-2 M^{PRO} with efficacy and binding energies equivalent to an already claimed N3 protease inhibitor. Similar to N3 inhibitor, Wi-N and CAPE were interacting with the highly conserved residues of the proteases of coronaviruses. The binding stability of these molecules was further analyzed using molecular dynamics simulations. The binding free

energies calculated using MM/GBSA for N3 inhibitor, CAPE and Wi-N were also comparable. Data presented by the authors predicted that these natural compounds may possess the potential to inhibit the functional activity of SARS-CoV-2 protease which is an essential protein for virus survival⁵.

In August, 2020 Adem and coworkers screened a library of 27 **caffeic-acid derivatives** against 5 proteins of SARS-CoV-2 by using Molegro Virtual Docker 7 to obtain the binding energies and interactions between compounds and SARS-CoV-2 proteins. The results uncovered khainaoside C, 6-O-Caffeoylarbutin, khainaoside B, khainaoside C and vitexfolin A as potent modulators of COVID-19 possessing more binding energies than nelfinavir against COVID-19 M^{pro}, Nsp15, SARS-CoV-2 spike S2 subunit, spike open state and closed state structure. Calceolarioside B was identified as pan inhibitor, showing strong molecular interactions with all proteins except SARS-CoV-2 spike glycoprotein closed state⁶.

In October, 2020 Khalil and Tazeddinova published a review on the most highlighted polyphenolic compounds present in up to date literature and their specific antiviral perceptive properties that might enhance the body immunity facing COVID-19, and

other viral infectious diseases. Authors concluded that **caffeic acid and its derivatives** have uncountable antiviral activities that may be used against the spread of emerging COVID-19 and its related symptoms⁷.

CONCLUSION

Caffeic acid and its derivatives may be used against the spread of SARS-CoV-2 and should be tested as prophylaxis and treatment of COVID-19.

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